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Investigating the effect of industrial wastewater and wastewater treatment on sustainable development

Pourya Zarshenas

Department of Inorganic Chemistry

Faculty of Chemistry & Petroleum Sciences, Shahid Beheshti University (SBU), Iran

pouryazarshenas@yahoo.com

Abstract

Freshwater resources in the world are limited and vulnerable. These limited resources have special economic value along with social, economic and environmental effects. With the growth of cities and their population on the one hand and the expansion of industries and factories on the other hand, the issue of environmental pollution is becoming more important day by day with the expansion of machine life and due to people not paying attention to everyone's interests. Environmental pollution makes humans and animals unhealthier and puts their lives at serious risk. Sustainable development is by definition a development that meets today's needs without affecting the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. Sustainable development is, in fact, balancing development with the environment. Sustainable development focuses not only on the environmental aspect but also on its social and economic aspects. Sustainable development is the intersection of society, economy and environment.

Keyword: Water treatment, effluent, wastewater, nano, treatment plant